

ABSENTEE VOTING IN LIMITED LIABILITY COMPANIES IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW DOES IT WORK?

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Abstract

Currently, many foreign individuals are interested in participating in the flourishing market of Uzbekistan through various means, such as purchasing shares of joint-stock ventures, bonds, investing in construction, start-up, and innovative projects, among others. Similarly, becoming a participant in a limited liability company is an effective way to participate in the Uzbekistan market as well. To have a voice in a company, participants need to have the right to vote in the general meeting of participants of a company. However, not every participant of a company can be in the same geographical location whenever a general meeting of participants takes place.

This paper analyzes how participants of companies can vote in a general meeting of participants without being physically present in the same geographical location.

Key words

Absentee voting, limited liability company, shareholder, participant.

1 introduction

Absentee voting refers to a decision-making procedure where members (participants/shareholders) of a company vote on issues **without being physically present at a meeting**. Instead, they submit their votes in writing, electronically, or by other legally accepted remote means.

In Limited Liability Companies (hereinafter – LLCs), absentee voting is used to adopt resolutions on company matters without organizing a formal meeting. This allows LLCs better flexibility and faster decision-making. It works well, especially when participants of a company are located in different geographical locations or during emergency situations. Today, in the flourishing economy era of Uzbekistan, many foreign individuals are interested in becoming participants of companies located in Uzbekistan, thus absentee voting is gaining greater significance in corporate governance.

Pursuant to Article 36 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Limited Liability Companies”, exchange of information during the absentee voting process can be done via the following means:

1. postal;
2. telegraph;
3. teletype;
4. telephone;
5. electronic or other means of communication that ensures the authenticity of the transmitted and received messages and their documentary confirmation.

II Legal framework in Uzbekistan

The main regulative law on absentee voting is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Limited Liability Companies”. However, this law only highlights the presence of absence voting, but not its procedure (e.g. how it is done?). This is why, currently LLCs in Uzbekistan themselves need to draft their own procedural rules regarding absentee voting and exhibit it in their charters or other local or internal documents.

Moreover, there is also one law that should not be disregarded. This is the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Electronic Document Management”, which regulates the field of electronic documents in Uzbekistan. When absentee votes are processed via electronic means of communication, all actions must be complied with this law.

III Mechanism and Procedure

As there is no law on regulation of the mechanism and procedure of absentee voting in Uzbekistan, companies themselves need to draft those rules and highlight them in their charters. See below a proposed example of mechanism and procedure of absentee voting on the following table:

Step	Key point
Initiation	e.g. By director, supervisory board or major participants (to be stated in the charter of a company)
Notification	e.g. By post or electronic means (to be stated in the charter of a company)
Voting	e.g. Paper-based or electronic ballot (to be stated in the charter of a company)
Deadline	To be decided in the charter
Counting and result	e.g. Counted by executive body (to be stated in the charter of a company)
Legal validity	Must comply with the procedural rules in the charter of an LLC

IV Comparative analysis

Meanwhile Uzbek law does not have a specific regulation regarding the procedure of absentee voting, Russian law provides a detailed one.

Pursuant to [Article 13 of the Resolution of the Government of the Russian Federation of 15.06.2024 No. 810](#), conducting absentee voting in LLCs in Russia is allowed. Specifically, according to the provisions in the article, mechanism and procedure of absence voting in Russia looks like the following:

Step	Key point
Deadline for sending ballots to voters	At least 15 days prior to the deadline for receiving votes
Form of a ballot	Ballot shall include: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- name and address of LLC;- a format of the general meeting of participants- a deadline for voting and address to where ballots should be directed;- options for voting in forms of “in favor”, “against” and “abstaining”;- a reminder that the ballot should be signed by a voter (participant)
Counting	Individuals who are responsible for receiving ballots are also responsible for counting them
Deadline for protocol	Protocol should be drafted and signed no later than 15 days after the completion of receiving ballots
Form of a protocol	Protocol shall include: <ul style="list-style-type: none">- name and address of an LLC;- format of the general meeting of participants;- date of a deadline for receiving ballots;- postal address to where ballots are directed;- agenda of the general meeting;- data about participants who took part in absentee voting;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- overall number of votes;- questions/matters that were put for voting; in “favor”, “against” or “abstaining”;- number of votes for each question/matter;- data about people who were responsible for receiving ballots and counting votes;- data about participants who voted “against” a question and asked to submit this data to the protocol;- data about the process of the general meeting and voting, if a participant of the general meeting asks to submit it to the protocol;- statements of decisions made upon each question by the participants of the general meeting;- date of the protocol of the general meeting;- data about participants who signed the protocol of the general meeting
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V Conclusion

Uzbekistan does not have a specific regulation regarding the procedure of absentee voting, however LLCs themselves may include it in their charters. Since Russian law has specific and detailed regulations regarding the procedure of absentee voting, using the model of Russia for it would be a substantial way to complete it. However, the best way is to add provisions that regulate the procedure of absentee voting to the legislation of Uzbekistan. This would make the procedure more transparent and reliable.

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